

PRINCIPLES OF INTERACTIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

This article is dedicated to the principles of interactive language teaching.

Keywords: *language teaching, language learner, principles, communicative interaction, self-education.*

INTRODUCTION

Language is nothing but a source of communication, a medium of conveying our ideas to one another. Language is a set of human habits, the purpose of which is to give expression to thoughts and feelings. In this era of globalization, Information and Communication Technology, English has a special and predominant role in the communicative sphere of the world. It has a special identity in the field of education.

Language comes through discovery. In Language Teaching, this refers to the mode or manner in which language is used. Language has been considered man's most remarkable achievement. It is the essential research resource for language professionals providing a rich and expert overview of research in the field of second language teaching and learning. Therefore, present unit will through light upon different principles of teaching English in school curriculum.

METHODOLOGY

In most countries, English is taught as a second language and as a foreign language. For English teacher, it is essential to teach in such a manner that desired goals can be achieved. Therefore, a sound knowledge of the principles of teaching English language is needed. Many scholars have given different classification of

principles of language teaching at secondary level but they can be grouped into three major categories.

Principle of Interactive Language Teaching

Principle 1: The student is the language learner. In learning a language, their own or another, each learner must develop and consolidate mental representations that are basic to understanding the language as well as to expressing oneself through it, whether in speech or writing. The radical paradox was echoed in Gattegno (1972), he observed that in teaching we are nurturing in learner's inner criteria that enable them to advance in their learning. "Only self-education," he said, "will lead any learner to the mastery of a skill." Students must realize they are responsible for their own learning; they will take this responsibility more seriously if they themselves discover and work at their own weaknesses and insufficiencies.

Principle 2: Language learning and teaching are shaped by student needs and objectives in particular circumstances. Student needs and objectives are not just personal. They are shaped to a considerable degree by societal pressures, political exigencies, and parental expectations influenced by these two. Social forces and community-wide perceptions, whether reflecting reality or merely hopes and fears, exert a largely subconscious influence on what are perceived as individual choices.

One such subtle influence is that of perceived career opportunities for the language learner; these changes over time, as economies and political alliances shift in emphasis, and this affects demand for particular languages. In all language teaching decisions, the question Who? (Who are my students?) precedes What? (What kind of course or learning materials do they need?), and these two determine How? (What approach and which techniques are most appropriate in this situation?)

Principle 3: Language learning and teaching are based on normal uses of language, with communication of meanings (in oral or written form) basic to all strategies and techniques. To learn a language naturally, one needs much practice in using the language for the normal purposes language serves in everyday life. This is in contradistinction to the artificial types of drills and practice exercises to which many learners are still subjected. Manipulation of structural patterns in some

presumed logical order in a sequence that is semantically incoherent does not prepare the learner for normal uses of language. Language practice should already be as close to real communication as practicable. Language in natural interaction requires more than correctly manipulated structures and lexicon, uttered with comprehensible sounds and intonation. It requires also conformity to the accepted forms of natural discourse within its associated culture: students need to know how to open and close conversational interludes; how to negotiate meaning; how to assert conversational control, fill pauses, interrupt or not interrupt, and navigate within the exchange so that the conversation is channeled in a direction of interest to the interlocutor.

Principle 4: Classroom relations reflect mutual liking and respect, allowing for both teacher personality and student personality in a non-threatening atmosphere of cooperative learning. An interactive language-learning environment requires that students and teachers, and students among themselves, reach a stage of being comfortable with each other, interested in each other, and respectful of each other's personal temperament-imposed limits. In order to achieve this equilibrium, teachers must feel comfortable with what they are doing, just as students must be comfortable with what they are expected to do. Teachers need to develop a realistic understanding of their own strengths and weaknesses as instructors and as individuals, selecting approaches and techniques that play to their strengths.

Principle 5: Development of language control proceeds through creativity, which is nurtured by interactive, participatory activities. The ultimate goal for our students is to be able to use the language they are learning for their own purposes, to express their own meanings, that is, to create their own formulations to express their intentions. That use of language is creative, not imitative, has been emphasized by language teaching theorists, linguists, and psycholinguists for years, yet many language teachers continue to teach as though imitation, repetition, and reconstruction or transformation of other people's meanings in exercises were the be-all and end-all of language learning.

Principle 6: Every possible medium and modality is used to aid learning. In communicative interaction, language learners need to draw on all kinds of

unpredictable items to express their meaning – items they learned the previous day, even items they learned on the first day they had contact with the language. What they have learned of the language must be firmly established in their memory networks with many associative triggers, so that it becomes readily available, in some cases for recognition in speech or writing and in others for retrieval for active use.

Principle 8: Testing is an aid to learning Testing has so often been punitive.

Students become very nervous about tests, which as often as not seek to discover what the students do not know or cannot immediately recall, rather than providing them with an opportunity to demonstrate to the examiners and themselves what they can do with the language. Many test-writers, unfortunately, concentrate on minutiae of language, looking for little slips or familiarity with lesser known grammatical usages rather than the broader aspects of comprehensible and acceptable language use. The test itself should be a learning experience that is part of the ongoing course.

If the test is to act as a guide to the student as well as the teacher, it cannot be final. The student goes on to relearn and consolidate what has been found to be lacking or misunderstood, and then has the opportunity to retest (not "be retested," since the decision is voluntary) to see how the learning is progressing.

CONCLUSION

In this unit, you have learned that language teaching refers to the mode or manner in which language is used. Language has been considered man's most remarkable achievement. It is the essential research resource for language professionals providing a rich and expert overview of research in the field of second language teaching and learning. You have also studied functions of language teaching and principles of teaching English language. All the principles stated basics of teaching English. In short, the children, their environment and their experiences, should be the starting point. Let them recall (and, they should be helped, if they fail) something familiar which is related to or contrasts with a new language item to be learnt.

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